

THE MONOTONY OF SMARANDACHE FUNCTIONS OF FIRST KIND

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Smarandache functions of first kind are defined in [1] thus:

$$S_n: N^* \rightarrow N^*, \quad S_1(k) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad S_n(k) = \max_{1 \leq j \leq r} \{S_{p_j}(i_j k)\},$$

where $n = p_1^{i_1} \cdot p_2^{i_2} \cdots p_r^{i_r}$ and S_{p_j} are functions defined in [4].

They Σ_1 -standardise $(N^*, +)$ in $(N^*, \leq, +)$ in the sense that

$$\Sigma_1: \quad \max\{S_n(a), S_n(b)\} \leq S_n(a+b) \leq S_n(a) + S_n(b)$$

for every $a, b \in N^*$ and Σ_2 -standardise $(N^*, +)$ in $(N^*, \leq, \cdot)$ by

$$\Sigma_2: \quad \max\{S_n(a), S_n(b)\} \leq S_n(a+b) \leq S_n(a) \cdot S_n(b), \quad \text{for every } a, b \in N^*$$

In [2] it is proved that the functions S_n are increasing and the sequence $\{S_{p^i}\}_{i \in N^*}$ is also increasing. It is also proved that if p, q are prime numbers, then

$$p \cdot i < q \Rightarrow S_{p^i} < S_{q^1} \quad \text{and} \quad i < q \Rightarrow S_i < S_q,$$

where $i \in N^*$.

It would be used in this paper the formula

$$S_p(k) = p(k - i_k), \quad \text{for same } i_k \text{ satisfying } 0 \leq i_k \leq \left\lfloor \frac{k-1}{p} \right\rfloor, \quad (\text{see [3]}) \quad (1)$$

1. Proposition. *Let p be a prime number and $k_1, k_2 \in N^*$. If $k_1 < k_2$ then $i_{k_1} \leq i_{k_2}$, where i_{k_1}, i_{k_2} are defined by (1).*

Proof. It is known that $S_p: N^* \rightarrow N^*$ and $S_p(k) = pk$ for $k \leq p$. If $S_p(k) = mp^\alpha$ with $m, \alpha \in N^*$, $(m, p) = 1$, there exist α consecutive numbers:

$$\begin{aligned} & n, n+1, \dots, n+\alpha-1 \quad \text{so that} \\ & k \in \{n, n+1, \dots, n+\alpha-1\} \quad \text{and} \\ & S_p(n) = S_p(n+1) = \dots = S_p(n+\alpha-1), \end{aligned}$$

this means that S_p is stationed the $\alpha - 1$ steps ($k \rightarrow k + 1$).

If $k_1 < k_2$ and $S_p(k_1) = S_p(k_2)$, because $S_p(k_1) = p(k_1 - ik_1)$, $S_p(k_2) = p(k_2 - ik_2)$ it results $i_{k_1} < i_{k_2}$.

If $k_1 < k_2$ and $S_p(k_1) < S_p(k_2)$, it is easy to see that we can write:

$$i_{k_1} = \beta_1 + \sum_{\alpha} (\alpha - 1) \quad \text{where} \quad \beta_1 = 0 \text{ for } S_p(k_1) \neq mp^\alpha, \quad \text{if } S_p(k_1) = mp^\alpha$$

$$mp^\alpha < S_p(k_1)$$

then $\beta_1 \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, \alpha - 1\}$
and

$$i_{k_2} = \beta_2 + \sum_{\alpha} (\alpha - 1) \quad \text{where} \quad \beta_2 = 0 \text{ for } S_p(k_2) \neq mp^\alpha, \quad \text{if } S_p(k_2) = mp^\alpha \text{ then}$$

$$mp^\alpha < S_p(k_2)$$

$\beta_2 \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, \alpha - 1\}$.

Now is obviously that $k_1 < k_2$ and $S_p(k_1) < S_p(k_2) \Rightarrow i_{k_1} \leq i_{k_2}$. We note that, for $k_1 < k_2$, $i_{k_1} = i_{k_2}$ iff $S_p(k_1) < S_p(k_2)$ and $\{mp^\alpha | \alpha > 1 \text{ and } mp^\alpha \leq S_p(k_1)\} = \{mp^\alpha | \alpha > 1 \text{ and } mp^\alpha < S_p(k_2)\}$

2. Proposition. *If p is a prime number and $p \geq 5$, then $S_p > S_{p-1}$ and $S_p > S_{p+1}$.*

Proof. Because $p - 1 < p$ it results that $S_{p-1} < S_p$. Of course $p + 1$ is even and so:

(i) if $p + 1 = 2^i$, then $i > 2$ and because $2i < 2^i - 1 = p$ we have $S_{p+1} < S_p$.

(ii) if $p + 1 \neq 2^i$, let $p + 1 = p_1^{i_1} \cdot p_2^{i_2} \cdots p_r^{i_r}$, then $S_{p+1}(k) = \max_{1 \leq j \leq r} \{S_{p_j^{i_j}}(k)\} = S_{p_m^{i_m}}(k) = S_{p_m}(i_m \cdot k)$.

Because $p_m \cdot i_m \leq p_m^{i_m} \leq \frac{p+1}{2} < p$ it results that $S_{p_m^{i_m}}(k) < S_p(k)$ for $k \in \mathbb{N}^*$, so that $S_{p+1} < S_p$.

3. Proposition. *Let p, q be prime numbers and the sequences of functions*

$$\{S_{p^i}\}_{i \in \mathbb{N}^*}, \quad \{S_{q^j}\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}^*}$$

If $p < q$ and $i \leq j$, then $S_{p^i} < S_{q^j}$.

Proof. Evidently, if $p < q$ and $i \leq j$, then for every $k \in \mathbb{N}^*$

$$S_{p^i}(k) \leq S_{p^j}(k) < S_{q^j}(k)$$

so,

$$S_{p^i} < S_{q^j}$$

4. Definition. *Let p, q be prime numbers. We consider a function S_{p^i} , a sequence of functions $\{S_{p^i}\}_{i \in \mathbb{N}^*}$, and we note:*

$$i_{(j)} = \max_i \{i | S_{p^i} < S_{q^j}\}$$

$$i^{(j)} = \min \{i \mid S_{q'} < S_{p'}\},$$

then $\{k \in N \mid i_{(j)} < k < i^{(j)}\} = \Delta_{p'(q')} = \Delta_{i(j)}$ defines the interference zone of the function $S_{q'}$ with the sequence $\{S_{p'}\}_{i \in N^*}$.

5. Remarque.

a) If $S_{q'} < S_{p'}$ for $i \in N^*$, then now exists $i^{(j)}$ and $i^{(j)} = 1$, and we say that $S_{q'}$ is separately of the sequence of functions $\{S_{p'}\}_{i \in N^*}$.

b) If there exist $k \in N^*$ so that $S_{p'} < S_{q'} < S_{p'+1}$, then $\Delta_{p'(q')} = \emptyset$ and say that the function $S_{q'}$ does not interfere with the sequence of functions $\{S_{p'}\}_{i \in N^*}$.

6. Definition. The sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \in N^*}$ is generally increasing if

$$\forall n \in N^* \exists m_0 \in N^* \text{ so that } x_m \geq x_n \text{ for } m \geq m_0.$$

7. Remarque. If the sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \in N^*}$ with $x_n \geq 0$ is generally increasing and bounded, then every subsequence is generally increasing and bounded.

8. Proposition. The sequence $\{S_n(k)\}_{n \in N^*}$, where $k \in N^*$, is in generally increasing and bounded.

Proof. Because $S_n(k) = S_{n,k}(1)$, it results that $\{S_n(k)\}_{n \in N^*}$ is a subsequence of $\{S_m(1)\}_{m \in N^*}$.

The sequence $\{S_m(1)\}_{m \in N^*}$ is generally increasing and bounded because:

$$\forall m \in N^* \exists t_0 = m! \text{ so that } \forall t \geq t_0 S_t(1) \geq S_{t_0}(1) = m \geq S_m(1).$$

From the remarque 7 it results that the sequence $\{S_n(k)\}_{n \in N^*}$ is generally increasing bounded.

9. Proposition. The sequence of functions $\{S_n\}_{n \in N^*}$ is generally increasing bounded.

Proof. Obviously, the zone of interference of the function S_m with $\{S_n\}_{n \in N^*}$ is the set

$$\Delta_{n(m)} = \{k \in N^* \mid n_{(m)} < k < n^{(m)}\} \text{ where}$$

$$n_{(m)} = \max \{n \in N^* \mid S_n < S_m\}$$

$$n^{(m)} = \min \{n \in N^* \mid S_m < S_n\}.$$

The interference zone $\Delta_{n(m)}$ is nonempty because $S_m \in \Delta_{n(m)}$ and finite for $S_1 \leq S_m \leq S_p$, where p is one prime number greater than m .

Because $\{S_n(1)\}$ is generally increasing it results:

$$\forall m \in \mathbb{N}^* \exists t_0 \in \mathbb{N}^* \text{ so that } S_r(1) \geq S_m(1) \text{ for } \forall t \geq t_0.$$

For $r_0 = t_0 + n^{(m)}$ we have

$$S_r \geq S_m \geq S_m(1) \text{ for } \forall r \geq r_0,$$

so that $\{S_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}^*}$ is generally increasing bounded.

10. Remarque.

a) For $n = p_1^{i_1} \cdot p_2^{i_2} \cdots p_r^{i_r}$ are possible the following cases:

1) $\exists k \in \{1, 2, \dots, r\}$ so that

$$S_{p_j} \leq S_{p_k} \text{ for } j \in \{1, 2, \dots, r\},$$

then $S_n = S_{p_k^{i_k}}$ and $p_k^{i_k}$ is named the dominant factor for n .

2) $\exists k_1, k_2, \dots, k_m \in \{1, 2, \dots, r\}$ so that :

$$\forall t \in \overline{1, m} \exists q_t \in \mathbb{N}^* \text{ so that } S_n(q_t) = S_{p_{k_t}^{i_{k_t}}}(q_t) \text{ and}$$

$$\forall l \in \mathbb{N}^* S_n(l) = \max_{1 \leq t \leq m} \left\{ S_{p_{k_t}^{i_{k_t}}}(l) \right\}.$$

We shall name $\{p_{k_t}^{i_{k_t}} \mid t \in \overline{1, m}\}$ the active factors, the others would be name passive factors for n .

b) We consider

$$N_{p_1 p_2} = \{n = p_1^{i_1} \cdot p_2^{i_2} \mid i_1, i_2 \in \mathbb{N}^*\}, \text{ where } p_1 < p_2 \text{ are prime numbers.}$$

For $n \in N_{p_1 p_2}$ appear the following situations:

1) $i_1 \in (0, i_1^{(i_2)}]$, this means that $p_1^{i_1}$ is a pasive factor and $p_2^{i_2}$ is an active factor.

2) $i_1 \in (i_1^{(i_2)}, i_1^{(i_2)})$ this means that $p_1^{i_1}$ and $p_2^{i_2}$ are active factors.

3) $i_1 \in [i_1^{(i_2)}, \infty)$ this means that $p_1^{i_1}$ is a active factor and $p_2^{i_2}$ is a pasive factor.

For $p_1 < p_2$ the repartition of exponents is represently in following scheme:

For numbers of type 2) $i_1 \in (i_{1(i_2)}, i_1^{(i_2)})$ and $i_2 \in (i_{2(i_1)}, i_2^{(i_1)})$

c) I consider that

$$N_{p_1 p_2 p_3} = \{n = p_1^{i_1} \cdot p_2^{i_2} \cdot p_3^{i_3} \mid i_1, i_2, i_3 \in \mathbb{N}^*\},$$

where $p_1 < p_2 < p_3$ are prime numbers.

Exist the following situations:

- 1) $n \in N^{p_j^{i_j}}$, $j = 1, 2, 3$ this means that $p_j^{i_j}$ is active factor.
- 2) $n \in N^{p_j^{i_j} p_k^{i_k}}$, $j \neq k$; $j, k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, this means that $p_j^{i_j}, p_k^{i_k}$ are active factors.
- 3) $n \in N^{p_1^{i_1} p_2^{i_2} p_3^{i_3}}$, this means that $p_1^{i_1}, p_2^{i_2}, p_3^{i_3}$ are active factors. $N^{p_1 p_2 p_3}$ is named the S-active cone for $N_{p_1 p_2 p_3}$.

Obviously

$$N^{p_1 p_2 p_3} = \{n = p_1^{i_1} p_2^{i_2} p_3^{i_3} \mid i_1, i_2, i_3 \in \mathbb{N}^* \text{ and } i_k \in (i_{k(i_j)}, i_k^{(i_j)}) \text{ where } j \neq k; j, k \in \{1, 2, 3\}\}.$$

The repartition of exponents is represented in the following scheme:

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where $p_1 < p_2 < p_3$ are prime numbers.

Exist the following situations:

1) $n \in N^{p_j^{i_j}}$, $j = 1, 2, 3$ this means that $p_j^{i_j}$ is active factor.

2) $n \in N^{p_j^{i_j} p_k^{i_k}}$, $j \neq k$; $j, k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, this means that $p_j^{i_j}, p_k^{i_k}$ are active factors.

3) $n \in N^{p_1^{i_1} p_2^{i_2} p_3^{i_3}}$, this means that $p_1^{i_1}, p_2^{i_2}, p_3^{i_3}$ are active factors. $N^{p_1 p_2 p_3}$ is named the S-active cone for $N_{p_1 p_2 p_3}$.

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$$N^{p_1 p_2 p_3} = \{n = p_1^{i_1} p_2^{i_2} p_3^{i_3} \mid i_1, i_2, i_3 \in \mathbb{N}^* \text{ and } i_k \in (i_{k(i_j)}, i_k^{(i_j)}) \text{ where } j \neq k; j, k \in \{1, 2, 3\}\}.$$

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d) Generally, I consider $N_{p_1 p_2 \dots p_r} = \{n = p_1^{i_1} \cdot p_2^{i_2} \cdot \dots \cdot p_r^{i_r} \mid i_1, i_2, \dots, i_r \in \mathbb{N}^*\}$, where $p_1 < p_2 < \dots < p_r$ are prime numbers.

On $N_{p_1 p_2 \dots p_r}$ exist the following relation of equivalence:

$$n \rho m \Leftrightarrow n \text{ and } m \text{ have the same active factors.}$$

This have the following clases:

- $N^{p_{j_1}^{i_{j_1}}}$, where $j_1 \in \{1, 2, \dots, r\}$.

$n \in N^{p_{j_1}^{i_{j_1}}} \Leftrightarrow n$ hase only $p_{j_1}^{i_{j_1}}$ active factor

- $N^{p_{j_1}^{i_{j_1}} p_{j_2}^{i_{j_2}}}$, where $j_1 \neq j_2$ and $j_1, j_2 \in \{1, 2, \dots, r\}$.

$n \in N^{p_{j_1}^{i_{j_1}} p_{j_2}^{i_{j_2}}} \Leftrightarrow n$ has only $p_{j_1}^{i_{j_1}}, p_{j_2}^{i_{j_2}}$ active factors.

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$N^{p_1^{i_1} p_2^{i_2} \dots p_r^{i_r}}$ wich is named S-active cone.

$$N^{p_1^{i_1} p_2^{i_2} \dots p_r^{i_r}} = \{n \in N_{p_1 p_2 \dots p_r} \mid n \text{ has } p_1^{i_1}, p_2^{i_2}, \dots, p_r^{i_r} \text{ active factors}\}.$$

Obviously, if $n \in N^{p_1^{i_1} p_2^{i_2} \dots p_r^{i_r}}$, then $i_k \in (i_{k(i_j)}, i_k^{(i_j)})$ with $k \neq j$ and $k, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, r\}$.

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